

A call for solid, reproducible data in clinical surgery

(combined efforts needed)

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Reproducibility Challenges in Contemporary Biomedical Research

The reproducibility crisis in biomedical research has been described and remains a substantial challenge in 2026 (1, 9, 12, 14, 18). Fundamental variables of surgical execution are not measured, not sufficiently controlled and therefore remain invisible (2, 3, 4, 13). Even well-designed trials often remain inconclusive because access to surgical performance data are missing and impede replication (5). Reproducibility fundamentally depends on the availability of homogeneous and controllable input variables and this requirement is particularly difficult to satisfy in surgical and interventional research (22).

The crisis is not uniform across disciplines. Fields where outcomes depend heavily on **human performance, like surgery, are more concerned and are at risk of irreproducibility**. Due to unmeasured variability in execution. In these fields, outcomes are critically influenced by the quality of intraoperative technical performance, a factor that is neither fully standardized nor adequately captured by conventional written protocols (11, 23). Consequently, apparent methodological rigor in randomized controlled trials (RCTs) may mask substantial hidden heterogeneity in the actual execution of procedures, undermining internal validity and comparability across centers (3, 4, 23, 24). Reproducibility is an unrenounceable request in science and presupposes homogeneous and controllable inputs (20, 22).

Variability in Surgical Execution

Written descriptions of surgical interventions are inherently insufficient to encode key determinants of performance such as precision of dissection, tissue handling, force application, timing, and intraoperative decision-making. As a result, when RCTs or real-world data (RWD) studies yield inconclusive or contradictory findings, it remains unclear whether these reflect true lack of therapeutic efficacy or variability in technical execution (6, 7, 23, 24). This limitation represents a structural source of irreproducibility in surgical science and contributes to the high proportion of trials that fail to generate actionable or generalizable evidence (5, 6).

Text-Based Protocols Fail to Ensure Homogeneity

Written protocols, today's standard, weakly capture technical performance and are scarcely useful for secondary scrutiny, they cannot be re-audited (11, 12, 14, 22). Furthermore, standardization based solely on written procedural protocols creates an assumption of technical uniformity that cannot be empirically verified. Deviations from prescribed techniques, compensatory maneuvers, and operator-specific adaptations remain undocumented and inaccessible to secondary analysis. This absence of objective procedural data prevents meaningful assessment of intervention fidelity and precludes stratification of outcomes according to technical quality, thereby weakening causal inference in surgical trials and observational studies (3, 4).

Visual Data are Basis for Transparency and Secondary Analysis

Objective and verifiable intraoperative visual documentation through systematic photo and video recording should therefore be considered a necessary methodological extension of contemporary surgical research (10, 15, 16, 17, 27). Visual data enable secondary scrutiny, retrospective assessment of technical quality, and more meaningful comparability across centers. In the era of advanced information technology, secure repositories for de-identified intraoperative visual data are technically feasible and compatible with principles of transparency and open science (7, 8, 13, 21). Such infrastructure would allow independent verification of procedural fidelity and facilitate multicenter benchmarking beyond textual protocol adherence. Objective, verifiable intraoperative visual data (photo/video) should be treated as raw scientific data, just like lab measurements. In the IT era, raw data can be placed on open repositories and extracted on demand. Peer review can include technical quality and AI based metrics can be developed.

Smart Instruments and the Future of Objective Surgical Metrics

The development and validation of quantitative metrics for surgical performance are urgently required to transform visual documentation into reproducible scientific evidence. Emerging smart instruments and automated capture systems already permit intraoperative recording without additional effort or time burden for the surgeon, providing a foundation for objective performance assessment and data-driven quality benchmarks. Automation of illustrated operative notes would be easy to realize and improve surgeon's motivation to produce solid data (9, 10, 17, 21). Integrating standardized visual documentation and performance metrics into RCTs and RWD-based studies may represent a critical step toward addressing a discipline-specific dimension of the reproducibility crisis and strengthening the reliability of modern clinical research in surgery.

Group effort to reach the goal

Big challenges persist to improve reproducibility in scientific publishing, especially in fields like surgery which is characterized by complex technical performances. Irreproducible and unmeasured execution variability is the main reason. Limited access to solid raw data is a key obstacle. Technical advances in data acquisition and automated analyses offered by AI are promising (8). Robust, verifiable and meaningful clinical data in surgery cannot be produced by a single group (surgeons), but are relevant for many different groups. Only a coordinated effort among hospitals, academic institutions, professional societies, regulators, publishers (18, 19) and industry partners interested in strong and reproducible data in surgery, can induce the needed changes. concerning several distinct fields respecting the principle of input related reward. A multi-stakeholder consortium could ensure rigorous evaluation, implementation, and governance (25, 26). Isolated actions of single stakeholders can only lead to unbalanced solutions (14).

Summary

A reproducibility crisis persists in surgery. Its specific structural cause is that the fundamental variables of intraoperative technical performance data are not measured, not shared and not controlled. Solid outcome-data can therefore hardly be expected and inconclusive trial results are not a surprise: Open visual documentation is not a luxury; it is an asset and a methodological necessity. Isolated actions of single stakeholders cannot induce changes. Only joint stakeholder-wide efforts will produce balanced, ethically sound, and verifiable solutions that strengthen the reliability of modern clinical research in surgery.

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